

“Make in India”- Challenges for Indian Managers

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Abstract: Since the time when H.E. Mr. Narendra Modi has chaired the seat of prime minister of India, the nation is on the path of high growth and development. “Make in India” campaign is one of the several example of this growth. “Make in India” campaign launched by the Hon’ble Prime minister of India, H.E. Mr. Narendra Modi has created a new vigor and enthusiasm in the youth India. This campaign will open up several opportunity for India youth in the industrial and manufacturing sector. This campaign will be helpful in reducing the unemployment in India. The GDP growth rate of the Indian economy will get the boost. All of these are the positive effect of this campaign but there is a dark side also. This campaign will pose new challenges for the Indian managers. Creating healthy business environment, development of skills, lack in research and development, creating labor intensive technology, increasing competitiveness of Indian manufactured goods, are some of the example of challenges that the Indian managers will face because of the campaign called “Make in India” launched by the Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi. If these challenges are tackled constructively, the growth of Indian economy will take a new pace. In this article, the author has made an effort to throw a light on such challenges.

Keywords: *Make in India, Challenges, Opportunities, Industrial And Manufacturing Sector, GDP*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Hon’ble PM of India, Mr. Narendra Modi has recently launched “Make in India” campaign on 25th Sept, 2014, at Vigyan Bhavan, New Delhi. The main focus of this campaign is to highlight the investment opportunities in India, particularly in the sectors such as Infrastructure Development, Energy sufficient, Manufacturing and skill development. The “Make in India” campaign will present new opportunities for Indian managers. Commenting on the launch of “Make in India” campaign, Siddharth Birla, president, FICCI said “We score embarked on the itinerary for India to transform globular manufacturing cause. Never before individual we seen so overmuch direction and attention on the essential manufacturing sector. This operation is a extortion to trillions of managers who effortlessly transmute over period to saw that India is certain germ of countertenor quality utter of the art products that attend the duty not exclusive at location but all over the world.”.

Thus, the “Make in India” campaign launched by the Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi is an opportunity for the growth of the country. But at the same time we should not forget that it will present several challenges also to the mangers of the country. In this paper, the researcher has tried to unveil such challenges ahead in the path of the growth.

About “Make in India” campaign:

In order to create India a manufacturing hub, the prime minister, H.E. Mr. Narendra Modi, launched the “Make in India” campaign at Vigyan Bhavan, New Delhi, on 25th September,

2014. The main aim of this campaign is to attract the foreign firms to set up the manufacturing units in India as a result creating greater foreign capital inflow in India. The launched ceremony was attended by top CEOs from Indian companies, international industry leaders, ambassadors, minister and government officials. A special arrangement was made to publicized this event globally in different world capitals. At the same time the same program was arranged in the state capitals and additional in Indian Mission abroad where officials engaged with the foreign investors and consultants.

Objectives of “Make in India” Campaign:

Following are the main objectives of “Make In India” Campaign.

- To get manufacturing sector grow over 100 percent on sustained basis.
- To make India a manufacturing hub for almost all manufactured goods.
- To bring inflow of foreign capital on large scale.
- To generate employment opportunities for the Indian youth.
- To create inflow of modern technology in India.
- To create inflow of labor intensive technology in India.
- To transform the economy from service driven growth model to manufacturing driven growth model.
- To unveil investment opportunities for foreign Companies, NRIs, Investment groups and Investment bodies.
- To create investor friendly environment in India.
- To make speedy infrastructure growth to create a strong base for industrial development.
- To make easy licensing provision and speedy approval of the projects through online portals.
- To integrate all central government services with an e-biz window online portals.
- To simplify and rationalize the regulatory atmosphere.

Coverage of “Make in India” Campaign:

The Campaign called “Make in India” launched by the PM Mr. Narendra Modi covers almost all the sector. The coverage of this campaign can be listed as follows.

- Biotechnology
- Automobiles
- Automobile components
- Aviation
- Construction
- Chemicals
- Electrical machinery
- Defence manufacturing
- IT and BPM
- Electronic system
- Food processing
- Leather
- Media and entertainment

- Mining
- Oil and gas
- Pharmaceuticals
- Ports
- Railways
- Renewable Energy
- Roads and Highways
- Space
- Textiles and Garment
- Thermal power
- Tourism and hospitality and
- Wellness

Thus, the campaign covers almost all the areas in which chances of development of manufacturing sector exist. This will help the country to grow at a faster pace in the industrial sector. The growth of the industrial sector will result in the overall growth of the Indian economy.

Infrastructure support for this campaign:

To make the “Make in India” Campaign successful, the government has already created a healthy infrastructural facilities for the speedy development of manufacturing sector. Below given are the highlights of this infrastructure development:

- More emphasize on the development of Industrial Corridors and Smart Cities.
- A new “National Industrial Corridor Development Authority” is being established to develop and supervise the Industrial Corridors.
- Delhi-Mumbai Industrial Corridors, Dholera, Shendra-Bidkin. Greater Noida, Ujjain and Gurgaon are the five smart cities in progress.
- Chennai Bengaluru Industrial Corridor: Master Planning for 3 new industrial nodes viz., Ponneri, krishnapatnam, Tumkur are in progress.
- The East Coast Economy Corridor is being commissioned with Chennai Vizag Industrial Corridor in its first phase.
- North-Eastern part of the country is to be linked with other industrial corridors with the co-operation of government of Japan.
- Development of new Industrial Clusters for promoting advance practice in manufacturing.
- Approval of 21 industrial project with the emphasize on use of recycled water through zero liquid discharge system and central Effluents Treatment Plants.
- Approval of 17 national investment and manufacturing zones.
- Creation of 1033 ports
- Further up gradation of IT facilities
- Application process made online
- Planned to train 144000 youth annually

These are just the highlights of the infrastructural facilities developed by the government. These are a lot more development made under this campaign.

Challenges against Indian Managers:

The “Make in India” Campaign is aimed at making India a manufacturing hub and the government is pulling out all the stops to make the investment smooth. The government has

created a dedicated system to answer all the queries of business entities with 72 hours. This system will closely monitor all the regulatory system to make them simple and rational.

The government has created a concept but the driving through this is not so simple. This concept will create several challenges for Indian Managers. The author of this paper has tried to disclose some of them below.

Creating the Most Enthusiastic and Dedicated Team:

The first and the most important challenge for the Indian Managers to make this campaign successful is to create the most enthusiastic and dedicate them. The managers will have to identify the hidden talent in the staff members who can dedicatedly work on the projects.

Creating a Health Business Environment:

Creating a health business environment is perhaps another challenge for the business development. It has been observed that Indian managers have been most stringent when it comes to innovation and development.

Creating competitiveness of Indian manufactures goods

Creating competitiveness of Indian manufactured goods is also a challenge ahead .It is found that Indian products cannot sustain in the foreign competitive.

To keep pace with technological development:

Fast technological advancement would be the requirement of the future dates. The Indian managers will have to keep pace with technological developments taking place abroad. This is perhaps one of the challenges for them.

New competition from several countries of the world:

The “make in India” campaign will create new competition from several countries of the world for the Indian managers. They will have to be ready to tackle this competition.

Development of skills and Talents:

Development of skill and talent in Indian managers and workers is another challenge. The managers will have to start skill development programs for the staff members.

Development in the field of research and development:

It has been observed that Indian enterprises are lacking in research and development. The foreign companies are more advanced in this field as compared to Indian companies. It will be challenging foe the Indian companies to make research and development speedier.

Creating labour intensive technology:

Creating labor intensive technology is another challenge against Indian managers. Since, India is a labor surplus economy, only the development of technology is not enough, but the labor intensive technology is required. If this is not taken care of, it will increase unemployment India.

Financial challenges:

Financial challenges are also very important point to be considered. It has been observed that the Indian companies prove to be weaker than the foreign companies in terms financial

consideration. The Indian managers are challenged to find out newer ways and means of generating finance.

Creating competitive atmosphere for the employees:

Creating competitive atmosphere for the employees is also required for the success of Indian enterprises in the competition of foreign companies.

CONCLUSION

In this way, “make in India” Campaign is a great opportunities for Indian economy, but at the same time it will pose certain challenges for the Indian managers. creating healthy business environment, development of skills, lack in research and development, creating labor intensive technology, increasing competitiveness of Indian manufactured goods, are some of the examples of challenges that the Indian manager will face because of the “make in India “ campaign launched by the prime minister Mr. Narendra Modi. If these challenges are tackled constructively, the growth of Indian economy will take a new pace.

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